

The Implementation of Covid-19 Control Policies and Communications in a Study-Port Area at Babang Harbor, South Halmahera Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the control of Covid-19 at the local government in South Halmahera Regency. The focus of the study was on the implementation of policies and communications on controlling Covid-19 by policy implementers in Babang harbour area. To measure the handling of Covid-19, the author reviewed the implementation of Covid-19 control and supervision in the port area. The author also analyzed the factors that affect the implementation of overcoming Covid-19. To objectively describe the empirical situation on the problem being studied, the descriptive analysis method was chosen. The technique of selecting the sample used purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by using observation techniques, in-depth interviews, and documentation studies. The data collection was carried out by triangulation of data and then analyzed using data reduction techniques, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of the study showed that the handling of the spread of Covid-19 in Babang harbor area at the beginning of the pandemic in 2020 was not optimal. This is because officers experienced a shortage of personal protective equipment such as N95 masks, hazmat clothing, Covid-19 test kits, hand sanitizers, and hand washing equipment. As for the factors that affect the handling of Covid-19 at Babang harbor, there were ineffective communication between implementing organizations, and complex implementing agencies as they involved representatives of the central government and local governments.

Keywords: South Halmahera, Policy implementation, Communication, Covid-19 control, Babang Harbor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) has affected on a crisis of governance and policies for overcoming the pandemic in Indonesia. Overcoming the virus spread at the beginning of the pandemic showed unpreparedness, so there was no adequate anticipation system when the outbreak had not yet spread. This is because the indifferent attitude of government officials to the threat of an outbreak and the absence of national guidelines for managing the pandemic situation. As a result, there is a governance crisis weak vertical and horizontal coordination, policy fragmentation, information confusion, and indications of public doubts over the country's capacity to manage crises (Mas'udi & Winanti, 2020:3-4).

The Central Government seems to be slow in giving official prevention appeals, so that some local governments take preventive measures based on their respective initiatives. Local governments that have controlled Covid-19 include the DKI Jakarta, Solo City, Central Java, and West Java (Masyur and Kartika, 2020:77). On the other hand, many local governments have also experienced the same thing as the central government in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic. In fact, it is exacerbated by limited human resources in the

health sector, financial capacity, and coordination between agencies and the health service system. This is what became the authors' focus in this study to analyze the handling of Covid-19 at the local governments level.

The establishment of the Covid-19 Handling Acceleration Task Force is to implement the Social Distancing policy in the community. The Task Force has four basic strategies in anticipating Covid-19, they are: 1) Using masks when being outside of the house; 2) Tracing of positive cases using rapid tests; 3) Carrying out education and self-isolation for some of the *tracing results* that show positive test results. 4) doing isolation in the hospital (Khodafi, et al 2020:102).

Restrictions on community activities are categorized into six activities, they are: a) school and workplace holidays; b) restrictions on religious activities; c) restrictions on activities in public places or facilities; d) restrictions on social and cultural activities; e) restrictions on transportation modes; and f) restrictions on other activities specifically related to defense and security aspects.

Referring to the above rules, the South Halmahera Regency Government has also formed a Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 to overcome the spread of Covid-19 in South Halmahera region. The geographical location of South Halmahera, which borders the City of Ternate and Central Halmahera Regency, makes access for people to and from South Halmahera be more elevating. This condition encourages the possibility of the entry of the Covid-19 virus brought by people from outside to South Halmahera. The entrance to South Halmahera from the sea and air was also tightened. Even in May 2020, the local government closed access to sea and air routes from and to South Halmahera. This aimed to suppress the spread of the Covid-19 virus in South Halmahera because in the neighboring areas such as Ternate City, there was an increase in the number of patients who were confirmed positive for Covid-19, namely in May 2020 as many as 59 people. Meanwhile, only 2 patients were confirmed positive in South Halmahera (kompas.com, 22 May 2020).

The Government of South Halmahera has taken a policy of closing the sea and air routes in accordance with the Regent's Circular Letter Number 360/47/SATGAS/V/2020 which explained that the temporary closure of the entrance to South Halmahera specifically for sea and land transportation for 10 days starting from 17-26 May 2020 (rri.co.id, 2020). This policy was taken because there was an increase in Covid-19 cases in Ternate which was feared to spread to the South Halmahera region. The government has implemented the closure of sea and air transportation routes to suppress the spread of Covid-19. This was in line with Minister of Health Regulation Number 9 of 2020 which allows the closure of transportation access to an area when there is an increase in Covid-19 cases in the area.

Based on the spread data of Covid -19 as of February 2021 in South Halmahera Regency, it can be explained that there are 565 confirmed Covid-19 patients, 318 recovered, and 10 people died (Corona.malutprov.go.id, February 2021). Covid-19 was first discovered in Wuhan, China. This virus causes positive victims to be infected in a short time. Its spread in Indonesia has occurred since early March 2020 and became the beginning of its spread in several parts of Indonesia (Khodafi, et al, 2020: 104). The spread of Covid-19 in Indonesia continues to increase. Based on data from covid19.go.id (March, 2021), the number of people in Indonesia who are positive for Covid-19 is 1,368,069, the number of people recovered is 1,182,687, and the number of people died is 37,026.

Monitoring of Covid-19 Data in North Maluku Province and South Halmahera Regency

Confirmed	Active Case	Healed	Die
North Maluku			
3958	516	3330	112
South Halmahera			
565	0	318	10

Source: corona.malutprov.go.id, February 2021

The handling of Covid-19 at the local level especially in the port area in South Halmahera Regency is the key of controlling the spread of the Covid-19 outbreak in the region. In its implementation, it involves various

government organizations. The implementers of the Covid-19 handling policy are various actors and levels of government ranging from regional governments to the central government. The central government representative organizations in the port area consist of the Port Health Office (KKP) from the Ministry of Health and the Port Organizing Unit (UPP) from the Ministry of Transportation. These actors in the review of policy implementation studies are policy implementers who determine the success or failure of policy objectives, because the bureaucracy at this lower level is directly related to the community in providing public services.

Various actors and levels of government who are involved in handling the Covid-19 pandemic are expected to control the spread of Covid-19 by sea. However, in reality there are several problems that hinder the governance process for handling Covid-19. The central government organizations in the regions and the South Halmahera Regency Government issued standard operating procedures for handling Covid-19. This illustrates that there is no one standard guideline that is used together in handling non-natural disasters Covid-19. Poor coordination among stakeholders in implementing this policy has become a classic problem. The Central Government has been too slow to provide guidance in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic. So that local governments tend to take their own steps to deal with the spread of the virus in their respective areas (Agustino, 2020:226)

This reality makes the coordination of handling COVID-19 at ports ineffective. Since each unit has its own chain of coordination, it affects the handling of the Covid-19 pandemic in the port area and South Halmahera Regency in general. Regarding the above reality, the researchers are interested in further analysis of the implementation of the Covid-19 handling policy in the port area in South Halmahera Regency. This study, therefore, aims to explain implementation handling deployment Covid-19 in Harbor Gaping Regency Halmahera South and explain about factors which affect the implementation of the Covid-19 handling policy in the port area of Babang.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

PUBLIC POLICY

Public policy is a science that covers various scientific studies such as economics, social science, psychology, and political science. Therefore, the notion of public policy will vary and depend on which point of view the position is interpreted. Dye explained that public policy is whatever governments choose to do or not to do. Dye (Subarsono: 2005) also revealed that a decision made by the government is a public policy because the government has the authority to issue authoritative decisions. Dunn (2000:132) interprets public policy as collective choices that are interrelated and become complex patterns of dependence, including choices of decisions not to do anything designed by government agencies.

POLICY IMPLEMENTATION CONCEPT

Agustino (2010:139) reveals that "implementation is a dynamic process, where policy implementers carry out an activity, so that in the end they will get a result that is in accordance with the goals or objectives of the policy itself".

According to Purwanto and Sulistyastuti (2012: 80), the core of the purpose of implementing public policy is an activity to deliver policy outputs carried out by implementers to the target group as an effort to realize policy objectives. Policy objectives are expected to emerge when the policy outputs can be accepted and utilized properly by the target group so the policy results will be able to be realized in the future.

MODELS IN POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation model of Edward III (1990: 149-154) is that there are four variables that influence the successful implementation of a policy. These variables consist of communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure.

a. Communication

The communication variable is one that affects the success in policy implementation. Communication will determine the achievement of the objectives of implementing public policy. Where the effectiveness of a policy implementation is determined by the knowledge of decision makers about what will be done.

Knowledge of what will be done can work when communication is done between them well, so that any policy decisions and implementing regulations has to be communicated to the appropriate personnel department. Notifications about policy implementation must also be precise, accurate, and consistent. The importance of this notification is done so that implementers in the field can be consistent in implementing every policy in the community. To assess whether communication in implementation is running or not, there are three indicators that can be used to measure it, namely: transmission, clarity, and consistency.

1. Good interaction will be able to produce a good implementation as well, because there is usually misunderstanding in communication.
2. Instructions received by frontline bureaucrats (street level bureaucrats) should be clear and not confusing. The ambiguity of policy messages does not always hinder implementation. At a certain phase, policy implementers need flexibility in implementing policies. But on the other hand, this will provide room for abuse of authority that affects the achievement of the stated policy objectives.
3. The orders given in carrying out a communication must be clear and consistent in its application, because the giving of orders that often change will cause confusion for implementers in the field.

b. Resources

Resources are one of the variables that affect policy implementation, because resources are one of the important elements in policy implementation. Edward III (1990, 149-154) suggests that there are several indicators in measuring resources, they are:

1. Staff: staff is one of the main resources in policy implementation. Insufficient, adequate, or incompetent staff conditions in their fields also contribute to the failure of a policy implementation. Thus it is necessary to increase the number of staff followed by staff expertise in accordance with the competencies required in implementing a policy in the field.
2. Information: Information becomes a very important part to support policy implementation. The information itself consists of two types. The first is information relating to guidelines for implementing policies. Implementors must know this guide so that when they get orders and directions they already know the steps to be implemented. The second is information related to officers' compliance with government regulations or regulations related to the implementation of policies that have been passed. So, the officers in the field can comply with the law.
3. Authority: the authority is legitimacy for implementers in carrying out policies which is determined politically. When the authority possessed by the implementor is small, their legitimacy in the public is reduced, so it can interfere with the policy implementation process. Therefore, the granting of authority to officers must be formal so that orders can be carried out. When formal authority exists, errors often occur in measuring the effectiveness of authority. For example, abuse of authority by officers for personal and group interests will have an impact on the effectiveness of the authority itself.
4. Facility. The existence of supporting facilities and infrastructure strongly supports the implementation of a policy. Even though the implementor has sufficient staff and understands what must be done and has the authority to carry out his duties, but all of this is not supported by the facilities, it will indirectly have an impact on the implementation.

c. Disposition

Disposition is one of the variables that affect the success of policy implementation. Edward III explains that in the disposition there are several important things, they are: 1) Appointment of bureaucracy; if the appointment of personnel by high-ranking officials in the bureaucracy who are not dedicated to the work, it

will cause obstacles in policy implementation. It is necessary to appoint personnel who are dedicated to the work that has been set. 2) Initiative, Edward stated that one of the efforts to prevent the tendency of officers to work not optimally is to manipulate incentives. In where the manipulation of officers' incentives will affect their performance in the field. Increasing their income by a certain amount will encourage policy implementers to work well. This step is an attempt to fulfill personal or organizational interests.

d. Bureaucratic Structure

To ensure that policy implementation can run successfully in the field, it must be supported by a good bureaucratic structure . Despite the availability of human resources, complete knowledge of officers regarding implementation, and the desire to implement a policy, there is a weakness in the bureaucratic structure, so the implementation phase cannot be carried out. In the implementation of complex policies, cooperation is needed, because when the bureaucratic structure is not conducive to implement the policies, this will affect the resources to be ineffective and hinder the implementation of policies. The bureaucracy as the implementing actor of a policy must support the policies that have been ratified by coordinating well.

Edward III revealed that there are two elements that support the performance of the bureaucratic structure in a better direction by implementing the following standards: 1) standard operating procedures (SOP) is a guideline for employees to carry out daily activities in accordance with the minimum standards set. set. 2) fragmentation is the assignment of responsibility for employee activities to several work units.

FACTORS AFFECTING POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

According to Van Meter and Van Horn (in Aneta, 2010:56-57), policy implementation runs linearly from public policy, implementors, and the performance of public policy itself. They suggest that there are six variables to analyze a policy implementation. They are:

1. Policy Size and Purpose
The success of a policy can be measured by looking at the size and objectives of the policy, whether it is realistic with the socio-culture that exists at the level of policy implementation.
2. Resource
Utilization of resources in an organizational unit as a policy implementer is very important to support the success of implementing policies in the field.
3. Characteristics of Implementing Agent
Implementing agencies involved in policy implementation consist of formal and informal organizations. The number of policy implementing agents follows the area and scope of policy implementation. The wider the scope, the greater the agents involve.
4. Attitude (Disposition) of the Implementers
Acceptance and rejection of implementing agencies will also affect the successful performance of public policy implementation. Usually rejection occurs at the implementor level because policy formulation does not involve people who are directly related and know very well the problems and problems they feel as the target group of policy implementation.
5. Inter-Organizational Communication and Implementing Activities
In implementing the policy, it must have a coordination mechanism to support communication between policy implementers. The better the coordination between the parties involved in a policy implementation, the mistakes can be avoided during policy implementation.
6. Economic, Social , and Political Environment
In implementing the policy, it is necessary to pay attention to the influence of the external environment. Van Meter and Van Hord said that the unfavorable economic, social and political environment could be the cause of the failure of policy implementation performance.

Researchers in the context of this study need to identify the factors that influence the implementation of handling Covid-19 in the port area so they can be explained more objectively in accordance with the findings obtained in the field. From the various variables above, the researchers chose several variables that will be used to analyze the factors that affect the handling of Covid-19 in the port area, namely: (1) Communication between implementing organization; (2) characteristics and implementing agents/implementors.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed qualitative approach with descriptive analysis method. The qualitative approach was used because it can elaborate in detail, authentic, and fundamental phenomenon being observed. Descriptive method of analysis used based on data and information which collected focus attention on phenomenon or problem actual through process collection data, composing processing, and withdrawal conclusion. So result can describe an empirical state and objective on phenomenon or the problem being studied (Agustino, 2020:255). The research was focused on studies regarding the handling of Covid-19 in the Babang Port Area, Regency Halmahera South. To analyze the handling of Covid-19 in the port area, the author was focused on seeing the response of the Babang port management organization in carrying out handling spread Covid-19. In the policy implementation in field, there are various factors that hinder. Some of the variables put forward by Van Meter with Carl Van Horn (in Aneta, 2010:56-57) entered as indicators that influence the implementation of policies, namely, communication between organization executor and characteristics and implementing agent or implementer.

Informants in this study consisted of people from government organizations who were given the responsibility to handle Covid -19 in the port area such as the Team for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 in South Halmahera Regency, KKP Babang Port, and UPP Class II Babang.

To check the validity of the data, the researcher used the triangulation model from Patton (in Moleong, 2011) . Researchers triangulated by comparing observational data with interview data, comparing interview results with the contents of a related document, and comparing the results of one informant interview with another.

Data analysis was carried out on the results of observations, interviews, and various documents that had been collected when the researchers went to the field. These various data were processed to answer the research problems. The data analysis technique used by Miles and Huberman (in Sugiyono, 2015) consists of three stages: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DESCRIPTION CONTROL OF COVID-19 IN SOUTH HALMAHERA REGENCY

Control of the spread of Covid-19 in South Halmahera Regency is carried out by the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 in South Halmahera Regency. The formation of this team follows up on Presidential Decree No. 9 of 2020 concerning Changes in Decision President Number 7 Year 2020 about Acceleration Disaster Emergency Response Handling Non Natural Corona Virus in 2019 and Home Affairs Minister Number 20 Year 2020 about Acceleration Handling Covid-19 in environment Government Area. So the government of South Halmahera Regency established task force for acceleration handling Covid-19 in South Halmahera region which involved stakeholders in government area, police officers and army force. The organization team was then formed at the sub-district, and village levels. So the effort Control of the spread of Covid-19 is expected to be carried out in an organized manner from level district government to villages.

The Babang Port area is included in the work area of the Covid-19 control acceleration team in South Halmahera Regency. In practice, in the field, the task force team coordinates with the Babang port manager.

Especially related with the supervision of the arrival of people (passengers) from outside South Halmahera. So the control measures at the port involve the district cluster team together with the port management officer. Where between port officers and the task force team is an inseparable part in carrying out the task of controlling Covid-19. Especially in monitoring and coordinating related to the implementation of health protocols in the port area in monitoring the arrival of people from outside South Halmahera.

In order to prevent the increase in the number of Covid-19 cases in Halmahera South, the South Halmahera Regency Government in May 2020 issued a the policy of closing the entrance for outsiders in South Halmahera for 10 days. This policy is stated in the circular letter of the Regent of South Halmahera with Number: 360/47/SATGAS/V/2020. Letter this explain closing temporary apply from May 17-26 2020. This closure is part of the control efforts the spread of Covid-19 in the South Halmahera Regency. Mainly control traffic of people who want to go to the Halsel area. Due to the condition of the case in Ternate City at that time experienced an increase, so the District Task Force Team South Halmahera issued this policy as an anticipation of the transmission of Covid-19 from City of Ternate to Halsel.

Closing access enter to Regency Halmahera South focused on all collecting ports, feeder ports, crossing ports for people, and boat moorings that serve services from outside the South Halmahera Regency. Road closures are also carried out on land transportation access, namely on cross roads Halmahera Among Regency Halmahera Middle, City Tidore Island, and Regency Halmahera South.

This policy of closing entry through ports and land transportation get denial inhabitant. Especially inhabitant Halmahera South which is at in City Ternate. They are disturbed by this closure, because they cannot carry out activity like usually. They forced stuck in Ternate During policy This entry closure is enforced. Rejection also came from the Chairman of the City Council Ternate, Muhajirin Bailusy. He said that this policy hindered activities Public and disturbing wheel economy between two region. So that need reviewed return policy closing access enter to Halmahera South. However Government Regency Halmahera South permanent doing policy this for the sake of safety of citizens from the spread of Covid-19 in South Halmahera. But after the period of this policy expires, the government will no longer continue to restrict access enter to Halmahera South.

Description case confirmed positive in Halmahera South

Source : public health Office Regency South Halmahera, 2022

Based on data on the spread of Covid-19 in South Halmahera Regency in 2020, it can be explained that the number of positive confirmed cases of Covid-19 from April to December 2020 was under 122 cases. Associated with the policy of closing access to South Halmahera which was carried out in May 2020, it has succeeded in reducing the number of positive confirmed cases in which the case of positive Covid-19 in May was as much 6 case. However, after this policy was dis continued, the number of people confirmed positive in South Halmahera in the month of June increased by 28 cases, then raised until 122 cases in July, and between August and December, the number of positive cases was 25, 37, 31, 70, and 80 case respectively (see chart 4.1). This shows that the spread of Covid-19 in South Halmahera in 2020 was still fewer than 122. This was due to the implementation of the health protocol for whole society, especially those who wanted to travel outside.

There is an increase in confirmed cases in the beginning of 2021. Data from The South Halmahera

District Health Office in January indicated that there were 192 people confirmed positive. However, this number continued to decline in February to June (see chart 4.1). When appear variant new Covid-19 that is Delta in Indonesia which followed with enhancement case, so the thing that same also happened in South Halmahera in which the number of positive cases of Covid-19 in July got a significant increase. If the number is confirmed positive in June as many as 164 people, so in July there were 845 cases confirmed. This is because the Delta variant is so contagious that it affects amount people who confirmed positive.

In side other enhancement case Covid-19 in South Halmahera Regency, this no miss from activity arrival person from outside especially the workers at mining in Obi Island and its surroundings, where the number of workers reaches thousands of people, so that when enter to South Halmahera region, people must conduct inspection of PCR and antigens test, so it was directly found out how many positive cases among the workers who returned to Obi Island. Then they are quarantined in places that have been set by local government.

To control the spread of Covid-19 in the South Halmahera region, Group Task Acceleration Control Covid-19 did various effort of prevention especially implementing health protocols in all public places starting from educational facilities, health, places of worship and crowded places that are potential cause crowd. Control of the spread of Covid-19 is also focused on the entrances to the area of South Halmahera, through the port of crossing for passenger ships and ships goods, then, the land transportation route between Central Halmahera Regency, KotaTidore Islands with South Halmahera Regency.

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE HANDLING OF COVID-19 IN BABANG HARBOR

The implementation of a policy that has been established is not forever running according to purpose. In the context of controlling the spread of Covid-19 in Indonesia, which is seen from the aspect of policy implementation, is indeed more inclined to top-down model because Government Center given authority to make policies related to the entire series of Covid-19 control in Indonesia. So the position of the local government, namely the provincial and district/city governments in Indonesia only wait down policy then held. It means local government, as policy implementer from handler Covid-19 in Indonesia.

Problems then arise in the field related to the implementation of the policy Covid-19 control in Indonesia. It takes too long for the bureaucratic structure to pass to the policy implementers. If it is described then it can be mapped that in the implementation in the field there are intersections between vertical organizations and local government organizations where in one control area consists of: a number of organization, for example in area harbor Gaping which involve organization vertical government center and organization government area. So that already can concluded that no easy to do various coordination for communicating the rule control of Covid-19 in field because each organization issued guide and standard operational procedure.

Implementation of the handling of Covid-19 in the Babang Port Area in 2020 did not work well. Various constraints faced by officer harbor especially related to the shortage of personal protective equipment for port officers, officer health harbor, and security who were on duty to do guardiance during the supervision of the spread of Covid-19 at Babang port as a the entrance to South Halmahera Regency. Not only that, the handling of Covid-19 in Babang port involves various agencies consisting of the Task Force Team Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 (South Halmahera Regency Government), Office Health Harbor (KKP) Babang, and UPP Class II Babang. Chain Coordination of handling related to various agencies certainly makes some communication is not going well because they have to follow the procedural of each agency. So it takes time to coordinate control Covid-19 in the field.

FACTOR OF COMMUNICATION WITHIN IMPLEMENTATION ORGANIZATIONS

In implementing the policy, there must be a coordination mechanism to support communication between policy implementers. The better the coordination in among parties involved in a policy implementation, then mistakes can be made avoided on during policy implementation.

Communication between implementing organizations is the relationship between organizations in handling Covid-19 in the port area which involves several agencies ranging from local governments to representatives of the central government in the regions. The handling of Covid-19 in the port area will involve the South Halmahera Regency Covid-19 Acceleration Handling Team, the Babang Port KKP, and the Babang Class II UPP. Smooth communication between policy implementers will encourage the achievement of the objectives of the Covid-19 handling policy in the port area.

On Step beginning control deployment Covid-19 in area harbor Gaping walk not enough maximum. Especially related with coordination about the need for personal protective equipment (PPE) for officers in the field. Where is every organization still focus cope his need each. Not yet there is coordination by integrated approach that is carried out to ensure the availability of all PPE needs for officers field in the port area. So that the officers in the field in handling Covid-19 handling at ports forced to use makeshift PPE or not worthy. Thing this of course very risky for officer. Because could experience transmission from the interaction process in carrying out their duties to handle passengers at the port. However thereby they permanent doing Duty in supervise and control various activity arrival and departure every boat in Babang Harbor.

This cross-organizational communication is not easy to implement. Especially coordination conducted on moment situation crisis pandemic Covid-19. All organization not yet have relevant guidelines in this Covid-19 pandemic condition. Every officer in the field are still waiting for instructions from their leaders. So it looks like the officers experience stiffness in build coordination cross organization. Because if mapped in the field, there are several organizations that have a chain of command different ones. For example, the Babang Port KKP and Babang Class II UPP are organization vertical in lower structure organization Ministry Communication and Ministry of Health. Of course, in carrying out the task of controlling Covid-19 in Indonesia, port areas should use the guidelines issued by the organization in on it. Whereas Team Group Acceleration Handling Covid-19 Regency Halmahera South containing various organization device area in environment Government South Halmahera Regency. Starting from the Health Service, BPBD, and the Police Unit civil servant Soldier (Satpol PP).

Stiffness communication in operating Duty control deployment Covid-19 This does not only occur at the lowest level, namely in districts/cities, in particular like in area harbor. Will but problem communication also occur in level government center. Because in process control deployment Covid-19 occur differences in policy responses taken by the Central Government. The government is considered slow to carry out protection and prevention by issuing policy guidelines implementation control Covid-19 in Indonesia. So that no amazed there is a number of local governments in Indonesia, such as the DKI Jakarta Government, which was issued a warning about the dangers of Covid-19. Where the DKI Government issues a number of guidelines for citizens and government organizations in dealing with entry the Covid-19 virus in the DKI Jakarta area. This is also followed by the local government others, for example the Tegal City Government and the Surabaya City Government and Semarang.

The portrait above illustrates that the bureaucratic structure has not been designed to deal with crisis conditions. Especially the crisis related to health problems, namely the spread of the Covid-19 virus, so that the same problem also occurs at the regional level, especially in the parts of the organization that have the task of carrying out services to the community. Personnel in the field experienced difficulties in communicating various matters related to efforts to control Covid-19. Because it doesn't have a clear guide. They just wait until the technical instructions on the procedures for controlling and spreading Covid-19 are issued, then the guidelines from the Ministry of Health are disseminated to the public.

Regulation handling Covid-19 in Indonesia also often fickle. The central government always issues the latest regulations in dealing with Covid-19, so that policy implementers at the regional level must quickly make adjustments and learn for yourself the meaning of the rules. This condition is different from usually, after regulation decided and run, so next conducted technical guidance for all relevant apparatus with these rules, so that they understand the essence of the rules that will be implemented to the community. But in time The Covid-19 crisis is different. Implementing organizations in the field are forced to understand the rules while doing various socialization of understanding the rules control Covid-19 through an online application.

Therefore the condition In the field, it is often found that there is recognition from officer that not yet accept copy rule which latest concerning with handling Covid-19. The officers need to wait a few days after the rules are issued by the central agency, only then accepted and studied by them. This condition also disrupts the communication process between organizations in the port area Babang in supervising and controlling Covid-19. For example, Tim Group Task Acceleration Handling Covid-19 Regency Halmahera South recommend closing harbor Gaping when occur increase case Covid-19 in Ternate around June-August 2020. However, when coordinated with port managers related to port closure efforts desired by The local government received a response that the total closure of the port was not can conducted. Because based on rule from Ministry Communication that harbor is object vital, so that closing harbor by total no held.

The difference in rules between organizations as above is one of the factors which make communication between executor policy often walk no effective. Because each organization use footing the rules each. However, when faced with conditions like this, policy implementers in the field then make a meeting to find the best solution. So it often occurs exceptions or policy discretion taken based on real conditions in the field. Discretion needed for support implementation from policy and could realize destination from policy the. Where in context control Covid-19 in the port area is still being carried out and the service of logistics ships and delivery of food and medical equipment for the purpose of handling Covid-19 also walk as should, although in a state of crisis Covid-19.

FACTOR CHARACTERISTICS AND AGENT IMPLEMENTATION

Agent executor which involved in implementation policy consist from organization formal and informal organizations. The number of policy implementing agents follows the area and coverage area of policy implementation. The wider the scope, the more effective agents involved the greater it is.

The implementation of Covid-19 control in the Babang port area involved several implementing agents, namely the Babang Port KKP and Babang Class II UPP. These two implementing agencies are vertical organizations under the structure of the Ministry of Transportation and the Ministry of Health. Then the South Halmahera Regency Covid-19 Acceleration Handling Team consists of various regional apparatus organizations within the South Halmahera Regency Government, starting from the Health Service, BPBD, and the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP).

The Babang Port Operator Unit (UPP) Office is a technical implementing unit within the ministry of transportation which is under and responsible for to the Minister of Transportation through the Director General of Sea Transportation. Task from UPP Babang is carrying out the regulation, control, and supervision of activities ports, safety and security of shipping at ports, as well as the provision of service service port which not yet worked out commercial.

UPP Gaping as wrong one agent executor control Covid-19 in area harbor also have obligation for ensure security and safety passenger especially in time pandemic Covid-19, however when doing Duty in the field officer experience limitations tool protector self. They forced just using PPE sober in doing Duty. Thing this shows that policy implementing agents in the field continue to implement his job for ensure policy the walk, although experience limitations PPE and personnel.

Office Health Harbor (KKP) Harbor Babang is organization in lower Ministry Health which called as units executor technical which responsible to the directorate General of Disease Control and Health Environment.

In dealing with the Covid-19 crisis situation, the role of the CTF is very important. Because has the task of controlling quarantine and epidemiological surveillance. Until the KKP prepare materials for planning, monitoring, evaluating, compiling reports, and coordination implementation quarantine and surveillance epidemiology disease potential plague. Not only that, at KKP there are environmental risk control officers and health which have Duty plan, monitor, evaluation, and make report, as well as coordinate with related parties.

When viewed from its duties, the existence of the KKP is very helpful in monitoring and controlling Covid-19 in the port area because the personnel available at in knowing their duties, especially in dealing with

the pandemic crisis conditions Covid-19. But on the other hand, the KKP also experienced a shortage of PPE when carrying out activities control and supervision of the spread of Covid-19 at Babang Port. Besides that, KKP has also been given the task of coordinating with relevant agencies like Team Group Task Acceleration Handling Covid-19 Regency Halmahera South. So that show that agent executor KKP this already have readiness by Duty in To do coordination. Although condition in field show that coordination related with distribution needs PPE not yet walk with good. Because all organization which handle Covid-19 experience deficiency PPE on while doing the task in the field.

V. CONCLUSION

The implementation of handling the spread of Covid-19 in the Babang Port area can be concluded, Handling at the beginning of the increase in Covid-19 cases has not gone well. Because officers in the field experienced various obstacles such as limited personal protective equipment (PPE), N95 masks, Covid-19 test kits, *hand sanitizer*, and hand washing equipment. However, over time the need for PPE began to be met by the government and assistance from the private sector. Then the handling of Covid-19 in the Babang Port area focuses on managing transportation modes, port managers, and ship passengers. For managers of transportation modes, port managers, and ship passengers, they are always supervised by officers in the field to continue to implement health protocols in accordance with guidelines issued by the government.

The handling of Covid-19 in the port area involving vertical agencies from the Central Government and the South Halmahera Regency Government has made coordination and communication in carrying out tasks not effective. Especially in the early days of handling Covid-19. Because all agencies are still focused on carrying out instructions from their respective superiors. In addition, the delay in the issuance of Covid-19 control guidelines is also a factor that affects communication between agencies in carrying out tasks in the field. The different characteristics of implementing agencies in terms of structure and authority also make coordination slow. Especially at the beginning of the implementation of handling Covid-19. The implementing agency consisting of the Babang UPP organization, Babang KKP, and the South Halmahera Government Task Force Team is a fairly large and dynamic agent characteristic. Because each agent is obedient and subject to the rules issued by their respective superiors.

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